

INSTITUT
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Pôle radioprotection, environnement, déchets et crise

Service de caractérisation des sites et des aléas naturels

COMPTE RENDU DE MISSION

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Lieu : Central Italy

Objet : Report on the "International Fieldtrip on earthquake faults in Central Italy - July 2017" and related trenches' excavation

Participants :

Stéphane BAIZE et Oona SCOTTI

Diffusion :

PSE-ENV/SCAN/BERSSIN : tous

PSE-ENV/SCAN : Vincent REBOUR

	Nom	Date	Visa
Rédacteur :	Stéphane BAIZE	28/09/2017	
Approbateur	Bérénice FROMENT	28/09/2017	

Introduction

The International Fieldtrip in Central Italy gathered about 120 earth scientists between July 19 and 22 2017 within the seismically active region where three damaging and deadly earthquake sequences occurred in 1997, 2009 and 2016, in the mountainous region between Umbria, Marche, Abruzzo and Lazio with breathtaking landscapes (Figure 1). The location of the visited sites is provided on the map in Appendix.

The motivation of the field trip (and the study of surface faulting evidences in general) is that surface faulting features are the superficial expression of the rupture at depth and this provides crucial information on the earthquake source. The study of current events, in terms of length of surface rupture, displacement amount, slip distribution, etc is a crucial step in earthquake-related hazards assessments.

The meeting was organized by several institutes (see http://convegni.unicam.it/TDEq_centralItaly), including IRSN. Information on this meeting, including program, abstracts and field guidebook can be found on this site.

Together with the Istituto Nazionale Geofisica Vulcanologia (INGV) from Rome, we (IRSN) excavated three trenches (namely the “Matthew”, “Curly” and “Hope” trenches) across the 2016 Norcia rupture, which were presented to the Field trip attendance. We opened, cleaned and studied these trenches in the 10 days just before the fieldtrip. With these trenches, we aim to assess the probability of rupture of the studied faults, estimate the penultimate age of the similar size earthquake and, if possible, the recurrence of such events. Results will be published as soon as possible.

This paleoseismological work is, together with the surface rupture mapping that will be soon published (Civico et al. and Villani et al), a direct input to the INQUA SURFACE project and a complementary study to the SURE Database that is under construction (see www.earthquakegeology.com for more information).

The field work in the trenches was done in collaboration with Paolo Marco de Martini, Francesca Cinti, Riccardo Civico, Fabio Villani, Luca Pizzimenti, Alessandra Smedile, Daniela Pantosti, Carlo Alberto Brunori and Marco Caciagli, all of them from INGV, and Jessica Thomas from RWTH Aachen.

Figure 1: A general view of the Norcia region hit by the 2016 earthquake sequence, from the Norcia fault-bounded basin to the west (left) to the fault-bounded intra-mountain Castelluccio basin to the east (right)

Organizing this in Italy was obvious because of the 2016 rupture and its amazing evidences, and of the richness of earthquake-related geology in the Central Apennines region. Central Italy is a very vulnerable place where you can grasp the impact of earthquake-related hazards.

A short session of presentations

In the Camerino University Campus, the meeting started with a welcome and introduction talks by Carlo Doglioni (head of INGV), Flavio Corradini (Dean of the University of Camerino) and Emanuele Tondi (head of geological department of Camerino University).

Geological background was provided by Massimiliano Barchi (University of Perugia) and Giusy Lavecchia (University of Chieti) who replaced the 1997, 2009 and 2016 earthquake sequences in the geodynamical framework of the Adriatic convergence and related “back-arc” extension (in the Apennines).

Lauro Chiaraluce (from INGV) detailed the seismicity and focused on the results of the huge work of relocation that has been done for the sequences. The outcome is of first relevance for imaging the fault geometry at depth which can be drawn for the whole fault system (over more than 100 km between L’Aquila and Colfiorito). Stefano Salvi and Roberto Devoti from INGV presented the geodetical results obtained for these three events.

The 1997 and 2009 earthquake sequences’ geology and surface ruptures were shown by Eutizio Vittori from ISPRA. Paolo Marco de Martini (INGV) described and analyzed the 2016 surface ruptures that appeared during each of the three events (24/8 M6 Amatrice, 26/10 M5.9 Visso and 30/10 M6.5 Norcia events). He pointed out the unique character of this cooperation between Italian, French and British geologists to create a common and shared database of surface ruptures after the M6.5 event (so-called Open EMERGE). Common papers will be soon submitted and hopefully published. According to Paolo Marco, with whom I completely agree, our community must take advantage of this successful experience to build a perennial cooperation at the continental scale.

At the end of the day, we presented with A. Michetti (U. Como) the INQUA activities related to earthquake surface ruptures.

1st Day - the 1997 Colfiorito sequence (Marche region)

From Camerino, the group was driven to the Colfiorito basin where the two shocks occurred. A first stop close to the Church “Santa Maria in Plestia” (which was damaged during the 2009 sequence) allowed the presentation of the earthquake geology of the area.

A discussion took place about the “hot topic” of maximum magnitude than can be expected in the region: some geologists defend that the geological and morphological information tend to limit this to $M=6$ for defined fault segments, whereas some attendees underlined that multi-segment ruptures are possible, increasing notably the potential earthquake magnitude.

A short visit to the Monte Faento fault was the occasion to observe the cumulative active fault scarp (Figure 2). During the 1997 sequence, a tiny evidence of earthquake-related displacement (which origin is

discussed by several authors: tectonic, gravitational?) appeared along this scarp with a 2-cm high white ribbon. More details about the surface rupture are given in Cinti et al. (1999).

Figure 2: Panorama (view to north) of the eastern border fault (Le Scalete segment) of the Colfiorito basin (red arrows) from the Monte Faento site. Right: the Monte Faento cumulative fault is marked by a steep scarp

The day ended by a visit of the Camerino historical center which was severely damaged during the October events of 2016 sequence (Figure 3), despite its distance to epicenters (20 and 30 km, respectively from the M5.9 26/10 Visso event and the M6.5 30/10 Norcia event). This is probably due to directivity effects (comm. pers. Lauro Chiaraluce) because Camerino is in the axis of the ruptured faults.

Figure 3: Few buildings suffered heavy damage in Camerino historical center

2nd Day - the 2016 Amatrice-Visso-Norcia sequence (Marche-Lazio-Abruzzo regions)

The procession of buses, vans and cars moved from Camerino south to the Norcia area. A first introductory talk was given at Forca Canapine site by Francesco Brozzetti (University of Camerino) (Figure 4): from there, one can observe the morphology of the Piano Grande di Castelluccio and the surrounding mountains (including the Redentore slope) where the primary fault ruptured to the surface during the 2016 earthquake sequence.

Figure 4. Left: scenic view of the Piano Grande di Castelluccio from Forca Canapine (view to north) with the Redentore slope in the background (right); right: the white ribbon (black arrow) underlines the cumulative fault trace that partly then entirely ruptures during the 24/8 and 30/10 events, respectively

The attendance then moved to the Fonte San Lorenzo valley where two out of three trenches have been excavated, studied and analyzed during the three weeks before.

The area was selected because of the presence of stepping-over “secondary (or distributed)” and antithetic ruptures that emerged in 2016 (Figure 5). We excavated these trenches to check the occurrence of previous Holocene ruptures on these “distributed” faults (Figure 6 and 7) and, eventually verify that they potentially ruptured together with a segment of the synthetic fault trenched at the “Hope” site. Our first order interpretation is that these faults ruptured in the past.

Figure 5: View to the west of the two-stepping ruptures in the Fonte San Lorenzo area and, in the foreground, the “Matthew” trench. The “Curly” trench was dug at the tip of the background rupture, behind the foreground slope.

Figure 6: A view of the “Matthew” trench, as presented during the field trip with our preliminary interpretation (picture from @Manuel_Sintubin). Red arrows depict the 2016 surface rupture.

Figure 7: View to the north depicting the San Lorenzo valley, dammed by the cumulative fault running at the bottom of the limestone slope. The “Curly” trench appears to the bottom left, intersecting the 2016 rupture. To the right, overview of the alluvial and organic sediments in the “Curly” trench.

The second half of the day was dedicated to hiking up to the ruptures on the Vettoreto (1 group) and Redentore (1 group, Figure 8) slopes. Another part of the attendance spent time along the rupture at the Forca di Presta and visited the “Hope” trench (Figure 9).

For more details on the M6 24/8/2016 and M6.5 30/10/2016 surface ruptures, check Pucci et al. (2017) and Civico et al. (submitted), respectively.

Figure 8: Close-up of the 24/8 + 30/10 earthquakes-related scarp (white ribbon) at the bottom of the cumulative fault scarp at “Scoglio dell’Aquila”, along the Redentore slope (credit: @Zoe_Mildon)

Figure 9: Scenic view of the Redentore slope with the 2016 rupture (red arrows) and the stepped synthetic segment of Forca di Presta where the “Hope” trench was excavated (orange fence)

Day 3 - the 2009 L’Aquila sequence (Abruzzo region)

The fieldtrip ended with an excursion to the L’Aquila area which was severely damaged during the 2009 M6.3 earthquake.

The first stop of the day was focused on a panoramic view from the L’Aquila highway eastern exit to introduce the geology of the area (Assergi Fault). Then, the attendance moved to the Paganica village to observe the surface rupture that occurred in 2009.

Two spots were introduced by Paolo Boncio and Luca Guerrieri. They presented the water pipeline outcrop where several active fault strands were identified, deforming Middle Pliocene to Holocene sediments.

This outcrop appeared when the 2009 surface rupture crosscut the pipeline, causing its disruption and the excavation of the shallowest layers by powerful water flow. The 2009 rupture (the youngest) occurred at the bottom of the cumulative scarp. The second stop is immediately south of the pipeline outcrop, in the courtyard of a private house. There, the small scarp (~10 cm) is still preserved in the topography and the 2010 trench open by INGV has been renewed for exhibition to the fieldtrip attendance. For more details on the L'Aquila surface rupture, refer to the publication EMERGEO (2010).

The day and the fieldtrip ended with a visit of the historical center of l'Aquila. Compared to my previous visit, the change is stunning. The government (and European?) funds were injected recently, the restoration of the monuments and buildings started and the city is a complete active workplace (Figure 11). Lead by the architect in charge of its restoration, we visited a private house -but classified as heritage building- located in via Bominaco which is currently under retrofitting.

Figure 10: Left: the small 2009 scarp is still visible in the field, few tens of meters south of the water pipeline; right: F. Cinti is happy to show us the continuation at depth of the surface rupture. She, with colleagues, evidenced several pre-events on the same rupture (EMERGEO 2010).

Figure 11: Historical center of l'Aquila, Piazza del Duomo

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Appendix

Location map of the visited area during the 3 days, including a seismotectonic sketch of the field trip zone with the main Neogene thrusts (black lines) and Quaternary/active normal fault systems (red lines). The Mt. Cavallo (MCT), Sibillini Mts (MST) and Gran Sasso (GS) thrust ramps are oblique to the main (N)NW-(S)SE trend of the normal fault systems. Extracted from the Excursion Guide Book.